

Street Hawking and Unethical Behaviours of Public Primary School Pupils in Uyo Local Education Committee

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Abstract

This study aimed at determining the relationship between street hawking and **unethical behaviours** among primary school pupils in Uyo Local Government Area. Three research questions were raised and three hypotheses formulated and tested at .05 level of significance. A correlational survey design was adopted while the population of the study comprised all the 6,619 primary two pupils in the forty-seven (47) public primary schools that make up the study area. A sample size of 360 primary two pupils was selected for the study, using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination table. A balloting method of random sampling was used in the selection of 20 sampled schools out of 47. Thereafter, 18 primary two pupils were selected from each of the sampled schools using the same balloting method of random sampling, which gives a total of 360 sampled respondents. The researcher's developed and validated questionnaire entitled "Street Hawking and **Unethical Behaviours** of Pupils Questionnaire (SHUBPQ) was used for data collection", with a Cronbach Alpha reliability co-efficient of .71 for unethical behaviours and .82 for items measuring street hawking. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics was used for data analysis and the study findings revealed a very high positive and significant relationship between use of intoxicating substances, pick-pocketing behaviour, truancy and unethical behaviours among primary school pupils in the study area. Conclusion was drawn from the findings while the researcher recommended among other things that, parents should not allow children to be involved in menial jobs and street trading activities, as such can promote pupils use of intoxicating substances and pick-pocketing behaviour.

Keywords: Street hawking, unethical behaviours, intoxicating substances and pick-pocketing truancy.

Introduction

Street hawking has emerged as one of the serious problems that have engaged the attention of scholars, professionals, social workers, and law enforcement officials. Many people are concerned about street hawking because it is an impediment to the proper well-being of children generally.

It is essentially exploitative and injurious to the physical, social, cognitive and moral development of the child. The International Labour Organization (ILO, 2012) approximates that there are more than 246 million children engaged in labour in the world. These children hawk in some of the most horrible conditions, where they face a serious risk of injury, chronic, illness, or death, kidnapping, rape among others. Children face safety and health hazards from carrying heavy loads, inhaling harmful dust and particles while hawking for their biological, foster parents or guardians. Street hawking exposes the child to a lot of hazards like sexual defilement, assaults, neglects and the threat of punishment for speaking out these social vices. Some of the dire consequences of these acts usually result in an unwanted pregnancy, sexually transmitted diseases, psychological problems and a gradual withdrawal from a healthy relationship with the opposite gender (Eboh, 2018).

Most developing countries including Nigeria, one in every three children hawk on the street for economic advantage. As noted by Okpa & Ekong (2017), pressures from street hawking reduce the ability of children to develop their potentials to full capacity, fulfill their life dreams and goals; hence, putting them under pressure to exhibit anti-social behaviours which are against the acceptable societal norms. A majority of these children are exposed to long hours of work in very dangerous and unhealthy environments. However, most parents encouraged children to work with their families, in order to learn skills, they would need in adulthood. Most parents recognize that activities such as doing chores around the home, assisting in a family business or earning pocket money outside school hours and during holidays can contribute to children's development and provide them with skills and experience that prepare to be productive members of the society during their adult life. Diallo, Bardasi, Beegle & Serneels (2013) argued that it is on this premise that some parents exposed their children to street hawking. In a bid to protect the rights of the child, the Nigerian government in 2003 formulated child's Right Act stipulating the minimum age for employment, yet, child labour and exploitation persists in both rural and urban areas due to underlying structures of poverty, inequality, social injustice, lack of decent work opportunities for adults, illiteracy among others (Ekpo & Ajake, 2013).

The prevalence of anti-social behaviour among pupils due to street hawking use has become very alarming. According to Ekpenyong & Sibiri (2011), pupils who always hawk experience problem of not attending classes or keeping up with their studies. Such truant behaviour jeopardizes chances of achieving their educational goals. Nwajiuba & Oni (2017) further noted that pupils who are exposed to street hawking often commit deviant acts like theft, burglary, robbery, sexual assault, vandalism of school properties, fighting among others. Many of the students' behaviours are tied to the peer culture; they imitate, admire and learn from the peers they like.

Street hawking among pupils can lead to a high tendency of exhibiting **unethical** behaviours, such as the use of intoxicating substances. The use of intoxicating substances refers to the consumption of alcoholic, tobacco and other psychoactive substances by juveniles. It is obvious that street hawking creates a feeling of false maturity syndrome in the psyche of children, which stimulates them to think, behave and consume what they see adults consume. According to Patience, Otu &

Ifeoma (2015), most pupils engaging in hawking gain knowledge of using drugs through interaction with people of questionable characters. The authors added that the use of intoxicating beverages such as marijuana, tobacco, benzodiazepines and other psychotropic substances among young people is alarming, especially, street children, orphans and child commercial sex workers. Young ones who are street hawkers usually indulge in taking these substances in order to prove their maturity.

Stealing or pick-pocketing is another unethical behaviour which street hawking might expose pupils into. Pick-pocketing is a form of larceny that involves the stealing of money or other valuables from the person or a victim's pocket without them noticing the theft at the time. As observed by Ajake, Etuk, & Omori (2010), most young pupils apprehended in cities in Nigeria including Lagos, Akwa Ibom, Calabar, Ibadan, Kano among others are due to pick pocket. The authors added that sometimes, these children perpetuate this acts by invading the window openings of trapped vehicles on bad roads or in traffic jams to raid passengers and even car owners of their belongings such as phones, monies, wristwatches, necklaces, and other valuable items catching their eyes. Such condition seems to occur because of parents allowing their children to hawk consumable and non-consumable items.

Theoretical and Conceptual Review

Hirschi's Social Control Theory (1969)

This study is situated on Hirschi's social control theory of 1969, which traces the incidence of illicit drug use or abuse among students in relation to four fundamental components of attachment, commitment, and involvement and belief system. As a general theory of crime and delinquency, the theorist began to study deviant behaviours by assuming that young one would violate norms and break the law based on their socialization or attachment with people. Hirschi argued that close associations with parents and siblings, law-abiding peers, and teachers or other school officials go a long way in controlling immoral behaviour of young ones. Attachment, commitment, involvement and belief are the four elements of a critical moral bond between the individual and society which would guard against deviance or risky behaviours.

Hirschi theorized that delinquent behaviours such as illicit consumption of alcohol beverages and other drug use commonly observe among pupils would be a likely outcome of ineffective ties to or improper socialization. This theory is relevant to this work as it proves the fact that the incidences of anti-social behaviours due to street hawking are an establishment of a weak moral bond between the pupils and their parents as well as the society. Pupils with strong attachment to family members and societal ethical principles are less likely to engage in anti-social conducts.

Concept of Street Hawking

The street child is defined as any child who may have parents or guardians in a locality but living and working in the street. Street children engaged in work or employment on a regular basis with the aim of earning a livelihood for themselves or for their families. Such activities are often carried out at the expense of schooling. According to Nseabasi & Oluwabamide (2010), street hawking is

a negation of the international convention on the right of the child. It is indeed inhuman for anyone to engage a child in money-making venture; such a child is denied basic education which is a right for every child. This could probably occur because their parents are from a low socio-economic background and may not place much value on their children's education. Ukwayi, Okpa & Akwaji (2019) described street hawking as a form of child labour which is caused by the quest to get rich, which propels young people, boys and girls into doing a lot of things they are not supposed to do all in the pursuit of livelihood instead of going to school.

Street hawkers do not endanger only the lives of the hawkers, but also the food hawked and the consumer society at large. Child hawkers spend most of their time outside the home in a bid to sell their wares (Mathias & Dada, 2013). They do not only hawk during the early mornings but at night and during harsh weather. Some of the hawkers are welcomed home with battering by their parents or caretakers when they could not make a profit from their wares or when they could not finish selling their wares. Above all, hawking affects the academic performance of the children. Eboh (2018) noted that most of the hawkers who hawk in the morning hours before going to school are perpetual latecomers. They lack concentration in class work due to fatigue and stress. These result in poor academic performance, delinquency and truant behaviour.

Concept of Unethical Behaviours

Unethical behaviours are actions that violate social norms and are usually of sufficient severity to warrant disapproval from majority of the society. According to Mason (2010), unethical behaviour is simply a process of differing from a norm or from the accepted standards of a society. Schaefer (2013) also defined unethical behaviour as a behaviour that violates the standard of conduct or expectations of a group or society. It involves the violation of a group norm which may or may not be formularized into law. In the opinion of Afuye (2015), unethical behaviour is any behaviour that lacks conformity and acceptability of the people in the society. The author added that unethical behaviour describes an action or behaviour that significantly contravenes the accepted or prescribed norms of a given society.

Street Hawking and Use of Intoxicating Substances

Drug is defined as any natural or artificial substance, other than food by its chemical or physical nature alters structures or functions in the living organization. In fact, drugs refer to the medicine prescribed by doctors or physicians. Drugs can be used for treatment, cure, prevention or diagnosed or diseases or used otherwise enhance of physical or mental well-being. On the contrary, intoxicating substances is the type of drug that is illegal to make, sell and used. These drugs include alcohol, cigarette, marijuana, cocaine, amphetamines, heroin and hallucinogens among others. Oshiokoya & Alli (2009) defined intoxicating substances are those substances considered by health authorities as illegal to sell or use because of their health implications which may result in hallucination of the consumer. Balogun (2010) described intoxicating substances as chemical substances used when it is not medically necessary or recommended by medical practitioners or

health workers, while Ogunsakin (2009) viewed intoxicating substances as drugs without regard to medically and culturally accepted patterns. Intoxicating substances are those drugs whose purchase, use and possession are termed illegal, depending on the society's definition.

The prevalence of unethical behaviour among school children due to use of intoxicating substances has become very alarming. According to Israel & Nyoho (2015), school children who always use intoxicating substances usually have problem of attending classes or keeping up with their studies. Such truant behaviour jeopardizes chances of achieving their educational goals. Marie & Zolitz (2017) further noted that children who are exposed to increase intake of intoxicating substances often commit deviant acts like theft, burglary, robbery, sexual assault, vandalism of school properties, fighting among others. Many of these behaviours are tied to the peer culture; they imitate, admire and learn from the peers they like.

Ubah & Bulus (2014) conducted a study on the effect of street hawking on the academic performance of students in social studies in junior secondary school in Nassarawa State, Nigeria. The authors found that street hawking predisposed students to unethical behaviour such as sexual abuse, marijuana use, excessive drinking, truancy, pick pocketing among others, which negatively affect their performances. Bolu-Steve, Fadipe & Kayode (2022) added in their findings that use of intoxicating substances, is commonly observed among school children that hawk consumable goods on the street.

Street Hawking and Pick-Pocketing Behaviour

Pick-pocketing is a form of larceny that involves the stealing of money or other valuables from the person or a victim's pocket without them noticing the theft at the time. Pick-pocketing is one of the oldest and most widespread crimes in the world. A skilled pickpocket can make off with just as much money as an armed robber, without much danger of confrontation or risk of being identified in a line-up. By the time the victim realizes what is happened, the pickpocket is long gone.

Street hawking has exposed many school children to pick pocketing and other anti-social vices. According to Wachikwu & Ibegbunam (2012), some school children who engage in street hawking usually practice inappropriate behaviours including pick pocketing. This act is a covert activity as many instances of stealing are not directly observed. Children, as they steal, consciously hide the behaviour from the property owner ensuring that nobody notices them. Nwanneka, Ikediashi & Akande (2015) found that among the anti-social behaviour display by school children due to street hawking, stealing, deceit and violence have become so alarming which negate the societal norms and values. The authors added that school children who engage in street hawking use to act on impulse, lose their temper quickly, and lie easily. There are usually found in act of bullying, cheating and stealing among others. The blame others for their misdeeds, feel picked out by their parents and teachers, and never seem to learn from their mistakes.

Johnson & Ihesie (2015) conducted a research on the social implications and factors associated with street hawking among children in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The authors found that school children who hawk on the street were more prone to pick-pocketing and other anti-social vices. Nwanneka, Ikediashi & Akande (2015) added in their findings that among the unethical behaviour displayed by school children due to street hawking, stealing, deceit and violence have become so alarming which negate the societal norms and values.

Statement of the Problem

Street hawking is a serious social menace affecting the moral development of young ones in Uyo Local Education Committee. The general standards of morality and social norms that govern acceptable patterns of behaviour are on the decline. Pupils who are supposed to be in the classroom during school hours are usually found hawking both eatable and non-eatable goods. Sometimes, the relationship pattern of speech and behaviours among these hawkers deviates considerably from socially desirable and acceptable standards of the society. Because of these unethical behaviours, the prospect of a better, safer and more prosperous and crime free society continues to remain elusive. These immoral behaviours, if not controlled may lead to these students growing up to become armed robbers, rapists, terrorists, cultists, ritualists and lawless individuals, thereby impending development and peaceful coexistence in the state. It is based on these observable problems that the researchers were keen to conduct a study aimed at determining the relationship between street hawking and anti-social behaviours among primary school pupils in Uyo Local Education Committee.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the relationship between street hawking and use of intoxicating substances among primary school pupils in Uyo Local Education Committee?
2. What is the relationship between street hawking and pick-pocketing behaviour among primary school pupils in Uyo Local Education Committee?

Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between street hawking and use of intoxicating substances among primary school pupils in Uyo Local Education Committee.
2. There is no significant relationship between street hawking and pick-pocketing behaviour among primary school pupils in Uyo Local Education Committee.

Research Method

Design of the Study

The correlational research design was adopted for the study. This design is used whenever the researcher wants to find out the magnitude and direction of relationship that exists between the dependent and independent variables (Udoh & Joseph, 2005). Therefore, this design was considered suitable for this study because it enabled the researcher to measure the interrelationship between street hawking and unethical behaviours of public primary school pupils in Uyo Local Education Committee

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised all 6,619 primary five pupils in the forty seven (47) public primary schools that make up the study area. (State Secondary Education Board, Uyo, 2023).

Sample and Sampling Technique

A sample size of 360 primary five pupils was selected for the study. This sample size was determined following the Krejcie & Morgan (1970) sample size determination table, which indicate that in population of 6,000 to 7,000, a sample size of 360 was representative of the population. A balloting method of random sampling was used in the selection of 20 sampled schools out of 47. Thereafter, 18 primary five pupils from each of the sampled schools were selected using the same balloting method of random sampling, which gives a total of 360 sampled respondents.

Instrumentation

The researcher's developed and validated questionnaire entitled "Street Hawking and Unethical Behaviours of Pupils Questionnaire (SHUBPQ) was used for data collection". The items were framed in line with the research questions and hypotheses. The instrument had two sections. Section (A) contained 15 items on unethical behaviours while section (B) contained 10 items on street hawking. The subjects were required to tick from a list of options as individuals, based on Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2, Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1.

Validity of the Instrument

To ensure the face validity of the instrument, three copies of the questionnaire instrument were given to experts for instrument validation. Two of the experts were from the Department of Psychological Foundations of Education (Measurement and Evaluation Unit) while the remaining one was from the Department of Sociological Foundations of Education, all in the University of Uyo to assess the suitability or otherwise of the items in the instrument. The inputs and corrections made by the evaluators and that of the researchers' supervisor were used to form the final copy for administration.

Reliability of the Instrument

To establish the reliability of the instrument, Cronbach Alpha reliability technique was used. Here, the instrument was administered on 20 primary five pupils in a selected school not included in the population sample. The instrument was administered and data were collated. Data was subjected to correlation and Cronbach Alpha statistics was applied for test of internal consistency of the instrument. This yielded the overall reliability co-efficient of .71 for unethical behaviours and .82 for items measuring street hawking. This index according to Udoh & Joseph (2005) is a high reliability index since the reliability co-efficient is above .50. Therefore, the instrument was deemed reliable for use in the study.

Method of Data Analysis

Data generated were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) to answer the research questions. The same statistical tool (PPMC) was used for testing of the null hypotheses by comparing the r-value with the critical r-value, so as to determine the significance of the relationship between variables all at .05 level of significance. The decision rule for answering the questions was adopted from Uzoagulu's (2011) interpretations as follows:-

Coefficient (r)	-	Relationship
± .00 to ± .20	-	Negligible, weak, very low, little or none
± .21 to ± .40	-	Present, slight, but low
± .41 to ± .60	-	Average, moderately high, fairly high
± .61 to ± .1.00	-	Very high

Results and Discussion of Findings

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between street hawking and use of intoxicating substances among primary school pupils in Uyo Local Education Committee?

Table 1: Correlation analysis of responses on the relationship between street hawking and use of intoxicating substances among primary school pupils

Variables	n	$\sum x$ $\sum y$	$\sum x^2$ $\sum y^2$	$\sum xy$ value	r-	Remark
Use of Intoxicating Substances	360	5768	90682	190757	0.78	Very High Positive Relationship
Street Hawking	360	6256	50416			

Result in Table 1 revealed very high positive relationship between street hawking and use of intoxicating substances among primary school pupils in Uyo Local Education Committee. This is

evidence on a correlation coefficient of 0.78. The result implies that pupils who are engage in street hawking are prone to use intoxicating substances.

Research Question 2

What is the relationship between street hawking and pick-pocketing behaviour among primary school pupils in Uyo Local Education Committee?

Table 2: Correlation analysis of responses on the relationship between street hawking and pick-pocketing behaviour among primary school pupils

Variables	n	$\sum x$ $\sum y$	$\sum x^2$ $\sum y^2$	$\sum xy$	r-value	Remark
Pick-pocketing Behaviour	360	5771	91426			
Street Hawking	360	6256	50416	189295	0.83	Very High Positive Relationship

Result in Table 2 revealed a very high positive relationship between street hawking and pick-pocketing behaviour among primary school pupils in Uyo Local Education Committee. This is evidence on the correlation coefficient of 0.83. The implication of this result is that pupils who consistently hawk goods are most likely to be involved in pick-pocketing behaviour and vice versa.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between street hawking and use of intoxicating substances among primary school pupils in Uyo Local Education Committee.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis on the relationship between street hawking and use of intoxicating substances among primary school pupils

Variables	n	df	r-value	r-crit	Decision
Use of Intoxicating Substances	360	358	0.78	0.196	Rejected H_0
Street Hawking					

Significant; $P < .05$; $df = 358$; critical $r = 0.196$

Result in Table 3 revealed that the calculated r-value of 0.78 exceeds the critical value of 0.196 at 358 degree of freedom and at .05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative is retained. This result implies that there is a significant relationship between street hawking and use of intoxicating substances among primary school pupils in Uyo Local Education Committee.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between street hawking and pick-pocketing behaviour among primary school pupils in Uyo Local Education Committee.

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis on the relationship between street hawking and pick-pocketing behaviour among primary school pupils

Variables	n	df	r-value	r-crit	Decision
Pick-Pocketing Behaviour	360	358	0.83	0.196	Rejected H ₀
Street Hawking					

Significant; P<.05; df = 358; critical r = 0.196

Result in Table 4 revealed that the calculated r-value of 0.83 exceeds the critical value of 0.196 at 358 degree of freedom and at .05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative is retained. This result implies that there is a significant relationship between there is a significant relationship between street hawking and pick-pocketing behaviour among primary school pupils in Uyo Local Education Committee.

Discussion of Findings

The researcher made a combined discussion of findings from the research questions and hypotheses of the study. Results from the research question one and hypothesis one revealed a very high positive and significant relationship between street hawking and use of intoxicating substances among primary school pupils in Uyo Local Education Committee. It is observed that pupils who are street hawkers are most likely to indulge in alcohol intake, smoking of marijuana and other substances in order to gain social acceptance and recognitions from friends. This finding is an agreement with the finding of the study conducted by Bolu-Steve, Fadipe & Kayode (2022), which revealed that use of intoxicating substances, is commonly observed among school children that hawk consumable goods on the street. This finding is also in tandem with the initial finding of the study conducted by Joseph, Joseph, Tella, Adekeye, Williams, Olokoba & Popoola (2019), which finding revealed that street hawking predisposed students to anti-social behaviour such as sexual abuse, marijuana use, excessive drinking, truancy, pick pocketing among others. It is observed from the above that street hawking increases pupils’ chances of involving in unethical behaviours such as use of intoxicating substances.

Results from the research question two and hypothesis two revealed a very high positive and significant relationship between street hawking and pick-pocketing among primary school pupils in Uyo Local Education Committee. This finding is in tandem with the finding of Johnson & Ihesie (2015), which revealed that school children who hawk on the street were more prone to pick-pocketing and other anti-social vices. This finding also agrees with the finding of Nwanneka,

Ikediashi & Akande (2015), which revealed that among the anti-social behaviour display by school children due to street hawking, stealing, deceit and violence have become so alarming which negate the societal norms and values. Therefore, it observed from this finding that street hawking can predispose young children to pick-pocketing behaviour.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is therefore concluded that street hawking has negative effect on school children, as it promotes use of intoxicating substances and pick-pocketing behaviour.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Parents should not allow children to be involved in street trading activities, as such can promote pupils use of intoxicating substances and pick-pocketing.
2. Government at all levels should legislate and implement laws against involving children in street hawking.

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